

ARALASH UZLUKSIZLIK MODULI BILAN ANIQLANGAN UMUMLASHGAN HÖLDER FAZOSIDA VOLTER O'RAMASI MA'NOSIDAGI OPERATORLAR

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Annotatsiya. Aralash uzluksiz moduli bilan aniqlangan ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning umumlashgan Hölder fazosida Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integral operatorning xossalari o'rganilgan.

Kalitli so'zlar: ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiya, Volter o'ramasi, integral operator, umumlashgan Hölder fazosi, aralash chekli ayirma.

OPERATORS IN THE SENSE OF VOLTERRA IN THE GENERALIZED HÖLDER SPACE DEFINED BY THE MIXED CONTINUITY MODULUS

Abstract. The action of the mixed integral operator of the Volterra convolution type in the generalized Hölder space of functions of two variables defined by the mixed modulus of continuity is studied.

Keywords: functions of two variables, generalized Hölder space, Volterra convolution type integral, mixed integral operator, mixed finite differences.

Kirish. Jahon miqyosida olib borilayotgan ilmiy va amaliy tadqiqotlarning salmoqli qismi, maxsus (singulyar) integral operatorlari amaliy xarakterdagi ko'plab muhim masalalarni, xususan, analitik funksiyalarning chegaraviy masalalarini, chiziqli va chiziqli bo'lmagan maxsus (singulyar) integral tenglamalarni yechishda uchraydi. Fazolardagi integral operatorlar nazariyasining eng muhim muammolaridan biri obraz silliqligining proobrazining silliqligiga bog'liqligini aniqlash muammosidir. Bunday masalani yechish integral tenglamalarning yechilishi, ularning barqarorligi va hokazolarda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Silliqlik tushunchasi turli atamalar bilan ifodalanishi mumkin. Funksiyaning silliqlik xossalari juda nozik tushunish usullaridan biri bu uzluksizlik modulining hatti-harakati nuqtai nazaridan shakllantirilgan umumlashgan Hölder xossasi tushunchasidan foydalanishdir. Bir o'zgaruvchili umumlashgan Hölder funksiyalar fazolarida bunday masalalar deyarli to'liq o'rganilgandir [2]-[8].

Ko'p o'zgaruvchili fuksiyalar fazosida bunday masalalar deyarli o'rganilmagan [9]-[15]. Biz aralash Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi integral operatorning xossalari ikki o'zgaruvchili umumlashgan Hölder funksiyalar fazosida qaradik. Ushbu maqolamizda bir o'zgaruvchili holda olingan natijalarga o'xshash yoki aynan shunday natijalarni olish mumkin yoki mumkin emasligini o'rgandik.

Materiallar va metodlar. Hozirgi vaqtda fan, texnika, iqtisodiyot va inson faoliyatining boshqa sohalarida, ayniqsa, elastiklik nazariyasi va kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar nazariyasida matematik usullar va kompyuter modellashtirishlardan foydalanish jadallik bilan kengaymoqda. Umumlashgan Hölder fazolarida kasr tartibli integro-differensiallashni o'rganishning muhim bosqichi bu Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholarni olishdir, ya'ni asl funksiyaning uzluksizlik moduli orqali kasr tartibli integrallarning uzluksizlik modulini baholash tushiniladi.

Uzluksizlik moduli bilan aniqlangan bir o'zgaruvchili Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi integralning Zigmund ma'nosidagi bahosini olish usulidan foydalanib, aralash uzluksizlik moduli bilan aniqlangan ikki o'zgaruvchili Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integralning Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholarini olamiz. So'ngra olingan Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholardan foydalanib, aralash uzluksizlik moduli bilan aniqlangan ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning umumlashgan Hölder fazolarini akslantiruvchi Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integral operatorning chegaralanganligi haqidagi teoremani isbotlaymiz.

1-ta'rif [1]. Agar $\omega(\sigma)$ ($0 < \sigma \leq l_0 = b - a$) funksiya quyidagi

- 1) $\omega(0) = 0$;
- 2) $\omega(\sigma)$ σ ning kamaymaydigan funksiyasi;
- 3) $\omega(\sigma)$ yarim additiv, ya'ni $\omega(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \leq \omega(\sigma_1) + \omega(\sigma_2)$;
- 4) $\omega(\sigma)$ $[0, b - a]$ da σ ning uzluksiz funksiyasi

shartlarni qanoatantirsa, u holda bu funksiya uzluksiz moduli deyiladi.

2-ta'rif [1]. Agar $(0, b - a]$ oraliqda aniqlangan $\omega(\sigma)$ funksiya quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa,

a) $\omega(\sigma)$ uzluksizlik modul funksiyasi;

$$b) \int_0^{\sigma} \frac{\omega(t)}{t} dt \leq C_1 \omega(\sigma);$$

$$c) \sigma \int_{\sigma}^{b-a} \frac{\omega(t)}{t^2} dt \leq C_1 \omega(\sigma);$$

$$d) \omega'(\sigma) \sim \frac{\omega(\sigma)}{\sigma},$$

u holda bu funksiya Φ^1 sinfga qarashli deyiladi.

2-ta'rif ([8]). $[0, l]$ da aniqlangan $k(x)$ musbat funktsiyani $V_{\lambda}, \lambda > 0$ sinfga qarashli deymiz, agar u quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa:

- 1) $k(x) \neq 0$, $x^{\lambda} k(x)$ - deyarli o'suvchi va $x^{\lambda} k(x)|_{x=0} = 0$;
- 2) shunday $\varepsilon > 0, 0 < \varepsilon < \lambda$ mavjudki, $x^{\lambda-\varepsilon} k(x)$ - deyarli kamayuvchi bo'ladi;
- 3) shunday C_1 mavjudki

$$\left| \frac{k(x) - k(y)}{x - y} \right| \leq C_1 \frac{k(x^*)}{x^*}, \text{ bunda } x^* = \max(x, y).$$

$\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ uzluksiz funksiya $Q \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, $Q = \{(x_1, x_2): a_1 < x_1 < b_1, a_2 < x_2 < b_2\}$ da aniqlangan bo'lsin. Quyida zarur belgilashlarni kiritamiz

$$\left(\Delta_{h_1}^{1,0} \varphi \right) (x_1, x_2) = \varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2) - \varphi(x_1, x_2), \tag{1}$$

$$\left(\Delta_{h_2}^{0,1} \varphi \right) (x_1, x_2) = \varphi(x_1, x_2 + h_2) - \varphi(x_1, x_2),$$

$$\left(\Delta_{h_1, h_2}^{1,1} \varphi \right) (x_1, x_2) = \varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2 + h_2) - \varphi(x_1 + h_1, x_2) - \varphi(x_1, x_2 + h_2) + \varphi(x_1, x_2). \tag{2}$$

Ikki o'zgaruvchili uzluksiz funktsiyalarning xossalarini o'rganishda biz quyidagi funktsiyalar sinfini qaraymiz [10]:

$$\tilde{H}^{\omega} = H^{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1}} = \left\{ \varphi(x, y) \in C(Q): \begin{aligned} &\omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, 0) = O(\omega_1(\sigma_1)), \\ &\omega_{\varphi}(0, \sigma_2) = O(\omega_2(\sigma_2)), \quad \omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) = O(\omega_{1,1}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)) \end{aligned} \right\},$$

Bunda

- 1) birinchi tartibli xususiy modul uzluksizliklar

$$\omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, 0) := \sup_{x_2 \in [a_2, b_2]} \sup_{0 < h_1 \leq \sigma_1} \left| \left(\Delta_{h_1} \varphi \right)(x_1, x_2) \right|, \quad 0 < \sigma_1 \leq b_1 - a_1;$$

$$\omega_{\varphi}(0, \sigma_2) := \sup_{x_1 \in [a_1, b_1]} \sup_{0 < h_2 \leq \sigma_2} \left| \left(\Delta_{h_2} \varphi \right)(x_1, x_2) \right|, \quad 0 < \sigma_2 \leq b_2 - a_2;$$

2) 1,1-tartibli aralash modul uzluksizlik

$$\omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) := \sup_{x_i \in [a_i, b_i]} \sup_{0 < h_i \leq \sigma_i} \left| \left(\Delta_{h_1, h_2} \varphi \right)(x_1, x_2) \right|, \quad 0 < \sigma_i \leq b_i - a_i, \quad i = 1, 2.$$

3-ta'rif. Ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiya $\omega(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa

1) tayinlangan σ_2 uchun σ_1 o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha $\omega(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \in \Phi^1$;

2) tayinlangan σ_1 uchun σ_2 o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha $\omega(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \in \Phi^1$,

u holda bu funksiya $\Phi^{1,1}(Q)$ sinfga qarashli deyiladi.

Bu sinfni ikki o'zgaruvchili uzluksiz funksiyalarning birinchi tartibli aralash uzluksizlik modullari sinfi deb ataymiz.

4-ta'rif. Agar quyidagi

1) $\omega_1(\sigma_1), \omega_2(\sigma_2) \in \Phi^1$ va $\omega_{1,1}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \in \Phi^{1,1}$;

2) $\omega_{1,1}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \leq C_{12} \min\{\omega_1(\sigma_1), \omega_2(\sigma_2)\}$,

bu yerda C_{12} – $\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1}$ larga bog'liq emas, shartlarni qanoatlantiradigan $\varpi = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1})$ uchliklar to'plamini $\Phi(Q)$ orqali belgilaymiz.

5-ta'rif. $\omega(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \in \Phi(Q)$ bo'lsin. Agar $\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ funksiya Q to'plamda aniqlangan va

$$\sup_{0 < \sigma_1 \leq b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, 0)}{\omega_1(\sigma_1)} < \infty, \quad \sup_{0 < \sigma_2 \leq b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_{\varphi}(0, \sigma_2)}{\omega_2(\sigma_2)} < \infty$$

shartlarni qanoatlantirsa, u holda bu funksiya $H^{(\omega_1, \omega_2)}(Q) = H^{\omega}(Q)$ sinfga tegishli deyiladi.

Ushbu $\omega_1(\sigma_1)$ va $\omega_2(\sigma_2)$ funksiyalarni $H^{(\omega_1, \omega_2)}(Q)$ umumlashgan Hölder fazoning xarakteristik funksiyalari deb ataymiz.

6-ta'rif. Agar $\varphi(x_1, x_2) \in H^{(\omega_1, \omega_2)}(Q)$ bo'lib,

$$\sup_{\substack{0 < \sigma_i \leq b_i - a_i \\ i=1,2}} \frac{\omega_{\varphi}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)}{\omega_{1,1}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)} < \infty$$

shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda $\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ funksiya $\tilde{H}^{(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1})}(Q) = \tilde{H}^{\varpi}(Q)$ sinfga tegishli deyiladi.

Ushbu $\omega_{1,1}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ funksiyani $\tilde{H}^{(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1})}(Q)$ aralash umumlashgan Hölder fazosining xarakteristik funksiyalari deb ataymiz.

$(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1}) \in \Phi$ xarakteristikalar bilan Q to'rtburchakning chegaraviy nuqtalarida nolga aylanadigan, $\tilde{H}^{\varpi}(Q) = \tilde{H}^{(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1})}(Q)$ fazodan olingan $\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ funksiyalar qism fazosini $\tilde{H}_0^{\varpi}(Q) = \tilde{H}_0^{(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_{1,1})}(Q)$ orqali belgilamiz.

Natijalar. Aralash Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi integral operatori quyidagicha berilgan bo'lsin

$$(\tilde{K}\varphi)(x_1, x_2) = \int_{a_1}^{x_1} \int_{a_2}^{x_2} k(x_1 - t_1)k(x_2 - t_2)\varphi(t_1, t_2)dt_1 dt_2, \quad a_i < x_i, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

1-teorema [10]. $k(x_i) \in V_{\lambda_i}$, $0 < \lambda_i < 1$, $\varphi(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0$ va $\varphi(x_1, x_2) \in C(Q)$ $i = 1, 2$, bo'lsa, u holda quyidagi Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholar o'rinli:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(\tilde{K}\varphi; h_1, 0) &\leq C_1 \left[h_1 k(h_1) \omega(\varphi; h_1, b_2 - a_2) + h_1 \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega(\varphi; t_1, b_2 - a_2)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 \right], \\ \omega(\tilde{K}\varphi; 0, h_2) &\leq C_2 \left[h_2 k(h_2) \omega(\varphi; b_1 - a_1, h_2) + h_2 \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega(\varphi; b_1 - a_1, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 \right], \\ \omega(\tilde{K}\varphi; h_1, h_2) &\leq C_{12} \left[h_1 k(h_1) h_2 k(h_2) \omega(\varphi; h_1, h_2) + \right. \\ &+ h_1 h_2 k(h_2) \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega(\varphi; t_1, b_2 - a_2)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 + h_1 h_2 k(h_1) \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega(\varphi; b_1 - a_1, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 + \\ &\left. + h_1 h_2 \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega(\varphi; t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2} k(t_1) k(t_2) dt_1 dt_2 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Ushbu teorema isbotini keltirmaymiz, uning isbotini [10] ko'rish mumkin.

Ushbu teoremadagi Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholardan foydalanib, aralash uzluksizlik moduli bilan aniqlangan ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning umumlashgan Hölder fazolarini akslantiruvchi Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integral operatorning chegaralanganligi haqidagi teoremani isbotlaymiz.

2-teorema. Agar $k(x_i) \in V_{\lambda_i}$, $0 < \lambda_i < 1$, $i = 1, 2$ va

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \int_0^{h_1} \int_0^{h_2} \frac{\omega(\varphi; t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2} dt_1 dt_2 &\leq C_{12} \omega(\varphi; h_1, h_2), \\ 2) \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} k(t_1) k(t_2) \frac{\omega(\varphi; t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2} dt_1 dt_2 &\leq C_{12} k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega(\varphi; h_1, h_2) \end{aligned}$$

bo'lsa, u holda \tilde{H}_0^ω fazoni $\tilde{H}_0^{\omega k}$ fazoga $\varpi_k(h_1, h_2) = h_1 h_2 k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega(h_1, h_2)$ xarakteristikasi bilan akslantiruvchi \tilde{K} aralash integral operator chegaralangan bo'ladi.

Isbot. $f(x_1, x_2) := (\tilde{K}\varphi)(x_1, x_2)$ bo'lsin, bunda $\varphi(x_1, x_2) \in \tilde{H}_0^\omega(Q)$. Agar $f(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0$, $i = 1, 2$ va

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{0 < t_1 \leq b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega(f; t_1, 0)}{t_1 k(t_1) \omega_1(t_1, 0)} < \infty, \quad \sup_{0 < t_2 \leq b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega(f; 0, t_2)}{t_2 k(t_2) \omega_2(0, t_2)} < \infty, \\ \sup_{\substack{0 < t_1 \leq b_1 - a_1 \\ 0 < t_2 \leq b_2 - a_2}} \frac{\omega(f; t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2 k(t_1) k(t_2) \omega_{1,1}(t_1, t_2)} < \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

bo'lsa, $f(x_1, x_2) \in \tilde{H}_0^{\omega k}$ ekanli isbotlash yetarli.

$\varphi(x_1, x_2) \in \tilde{H}_0^\omega(Q)$ bo'lgani uchun 1-teoremadan foydalanish mumkin. Ushbu teoreмага ko'ra integral (3) uchun Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholar o'rinli.

Teoremaning sharti va Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholardan foydalanib quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\omega_f^{1,0}(h_1, 0)}{h_1 k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)} &\leq C_1 \left(\frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(h_1, b_2 - a_2)}{\omega_1(h_1)} + \frac{1}{k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(t_1, b_2 - a_2)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_1 \left(\frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,0}(h_1, 0)}{\omega_1(h_1)} + \frac{1}{k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,0}(t_1, 0)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_1 \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma} \left(\frac{\omega_1(h_1)}{\omega_1(h_1)} + \frac{1}{k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_1(t_1)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_1 \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma} \left(\frac{\omega_1(h_1)}{\omega_1(h_1)} + \frac{k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)}{k(h_1) \omega_1(h_1)} \right) = 2C_1 \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma}, \\
 \frac{\omega_f^{0,1}(0, h_2)}{h_2 k(h_2) \omega_2(h_2)} &\leq C_2 \left(\frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(b_1 - a_1, h_2)}{\omega_2(h_2)} + \frac{1}{k(h_2) \omega_2(h_2)} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(b_1 - a_1, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_2 \left(\frac{\omega_\varphi^{0,1}(0, h_2)}{\omega_2(h_2)} + \frac{1}{k(h_2) \omega_2(h_2)} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{0,1}(0, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 \right) \leq C_2 \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma}, \\
 \frac{\omega_f^{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{h_1 k(h_1) h_2 k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} &\leq C_{12} \left(\frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} + \right. \\
 &+ \frac{1}{k(h_1) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(t_1, h_2)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 + \frac{1}{k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(h_1, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 + \\
 &\left. + \frac{1}{k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_\varphi^{1,1}(t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2} k(t_1) k(t_2) dt_1 dt_2 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_{12} \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma} \left(\frac{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} + \frac{1}{k(h_1) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega_{1,1}(t_1, h_2)}{t_1} k(t_1) dt_1 + \right. \\
 &+ \frac{1}{k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, t_2)}{t_2} k(t_2) dt_2 + \\
 &\left. + \frac{1}{k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \int_{h_1}^{b_1 - a_1} \int_{h_2}^{b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega_{1,1}(t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2} k(t_1) k(t_2) dt_1 dt_2 \right) \leq \\
 &\leq C_{12} \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma} \left(\frac{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{\omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} + \frac{k(h_1) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{k(h_1) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} + \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} + \frac{k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)}{k(h_1) k(h_2) \omega_{1,1}(h_1, h_2)} \right) = C \|\Phi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^\sigma}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Ya'ni

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{0 < t_1 \leq b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega^{1,0}(f; t_1, 0)}{t_1^{\alpha_1} \omega_{1,1}(t_1, b_2 - a_2)} &\leq C_1 \|\varphi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_1}}, \\ \sup_{0 < t_2 \leq b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega^{0,1}(f; 0, t_2)}{t_2^{\alpha_2} \omega_{1,1}(b_1 - a_1, t_2)} &\leq C_2 \|\varphi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_2}}, \\ \sup_{\substack{0 < t_1 \leq b_1 - a_1 \\ 0 < t_2 \leq b_2 - a_2}} \frac{\omega^{1,1}(f; t_1, t_2)}{t_1^{\alpha_1} t_2^{\alpha_2} \omega_{1,1}(t_1, t_2)} &\leq C_{12} \|\varphi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Bundan (4) ning o'rinli ekanligini ko'ramiz.

$\varphi(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0, i = 1, 2$ ekanligidan (1) va (2) tengliklardan foysdalanib, quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{C(\mathcal{Q})} &= \max_{\substack{a_i \leq x_i \leq b_i \\ i=1,2}} \left| \int_{a_1}^{x_1} \int_{a_2}^{x_2} k(x_1 - t_1) k(x_2 - t_2) (\varphi(t_1, a_2) - \varphi(a_1, a_2)) dt_1 dt_2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{a_1}^{x_1} \int_{a_2}^{x_2} k(x_1 - t_1) k(x_2 - t_2) (\varphi(a_1, t_2) - \varphi(a_1, a_2)) dt_1 dt_2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{a_1}^{x_1} \int_{a_2}^{x_2} k(x_1 - t_1) k(x_2 - t_2) \left(\Delta_{t_1 - a_1, t_2 - a_2}^{1,1} \varphi \right) (a_1, a_2) dt_1 dt_2 \right| \leq \\ &\leq C_{12} \left(\max_{a_1 \leq x_1 \leq b_1} \omega^{1,0}(x_1 - a_1, 0) (x_1 - a_1) k(x_1 - a_1) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \max_{a_2 \leq x_2 \leq b_2} \omega^{0,1}(0, x_2 - a_2) (x_2 - a_2) k(x_2 - a_2) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \max_{\substack{a_i \leq x_i \leq b_i \\ i=1,2}} \omega^{1,1}(x_1 - a_1, x_2 - a_2) (x_1 - a_1) k(x_1 - a_1) (x_2 - a_2) k(x_2 - a_2) \right) \leq C_{12} \|\varphi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Ushbu tengsizlik va (4) dan quyidagi kelib chiqadi

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}} &= \|f\|_{C(\mathcal{Q})} + \sup_{0 < t_1 \leq b_1 - a_1} \frac{\omega^{1,0}(f; t_1, 0)}{t_1 k(t_1) \omega_1(t_1)} + \sup_{0 < t_2 \leq b_2 - a_2} \frac{\omega^{0,1}(f; 0, t_2)}{t_2 k(t_2) \omega_2(t_2)} + \\ &\quad + \sup_{\substack{0 < t_i \leq b_i - a_i \\ i=1,2}} \frac{\omega^{1,1}(f; t_1, t_2)}{t_1 t_2 k(t_1) k(t_2) \omega_{1,1}(t_1, t_2)} \leq C_{12} \|\varphi\|_{\tilde{H}_0^{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}}. \end{aligned}$$

$f(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0, i = 1, 2$ tenglikni isbotlash uchun (3) tenglikda $t_i = x_i - (x_i - a_i)\xi_i, i = 1, 2$ kabi almashtirishlar olamiz, natijada

$$\begin{aligned} f(x_1, x_2) &= (\tilde{K}\varphi)(x_1, x_2) = \\ &= (x_1 - a_1)(x_2 - a_2) \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(x_1 - (x_1 - a_1)\xi_1, x_2 - (x_2 - a_2)\xi_2)}{[k(x_1\xi_1 - a_1\xi_1)k(x_2\xi_2 - a_2\xi_2)]^{-1}} d\xi_1 d\xi_2. \end{aligned}$$

$\varphi(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0, i = 1, 2$ dan

$$\begin{aligned} |f(x_1, x_2)| &= |(\tilde{K}\varphi)(x, y)| \leq \\ &\leq C_{12} (x_1 - a_1)(x_2 - a_2) \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \omega_{\varphi}(1 - \xi_1, 1 - \xi_2) k((x_1 - a_1)\xi_1) k((x_2 - a_2)\xi_2) d\xi_1 d\xi_2 \leq \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq C_{12} \frac{k(x_1 - a_1)k(x_2 - a_2)}{(x_1 - a_1)^{-1}(x_2 - a_2)^{-1}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\omega_\varphi(1 - \xi_1, 1 - \xi_2)}{\xi_1^{\lambda_1} \xi_2^{\lambda_2}} d\xi_1 d\xi_2 = \\ = C(x_1 - a_1)(x_2 - a_2)k(x_1 - a_1)k(x_2 - a_2)$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Bundan esa $x_i \rightarrow a_i$ da $f(x_1, x_2)|_{x_i=a_i} = 0, i = 1, 2$.

Xulosalar. Aralash uzluksizlik moduli bilan aniqlangan ikki o'zgaruvchili funktsiyali Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integral operatori uchun Zigmund ma'nosidagi baholari olinib, ushbu baholardan foydalanib, umumlashgan Hölder fazosida Volter o'ramasi ma'nosidagi aralash integral operatori xossasi o'rganildi. Bu natijalardan shuni xulosa qilish mumkin, agar qaralayotgan integral operator (4) ko'rinishda bo'lsa, u holda ikki o'zgaruvchili funktsiyalar uchun ham xuddi bir o'zgaruvchili funktsiyalarda olingan teoremlarga [8] o'xshash teoremani olish mumkin ekan.

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